

Single-aperture Patch Antenna with Pattern Control

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Abstract— Microstrip patch antennas are common for GNSS applications due to their low profile, small size, ease of fabrication, and low cost. Typically, the radiation characteristics of a single-element patch antenna are fixed, with an inability to electronically control the radiation characteristics in azimuth and elevation. This paper presents a single-aperture (i.e., single-element) GNSS patch antenna that can electronically control the radiation characteristics, by placing an area of high directivity with a commensurate area of low directivity in a particular direction that may be useful for interference suppression. Here, the performance of a circular four probe-fed GPS L5 patch antenna over a circular ground plane is illustrated with an amplitude and phase control subsystem for pattern control. The overall design approach is outlined and supported with computational electromagnetic model (CEM) simulations and measured results. The fabrication of the antenna is illustrated and the measured results at the component level and anechoic chamber radiation characteristics are presented to illustrate the pattern control aspects of the antenna. Gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is achieved at, above, and below the horizon in the commanded null direction, with gain suppression at the horizon varying from 4-13 dB and null depth varying from 22-35 dB. This control has a major advantage by controlling the radiation characteristic to allow for mitigation of interfering signals at, above, and below the horizon.

Keywords—patch; antenna; GNSS; GPS; Galileo; L5; E5; pattern; control; interference; jamming; null; CRPA; multipath; SDR

I. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip patch antennas, including single-element patch antennas are very common in GNSS receiver systems due to their low profile, small size, ease of fabrication, simplicity, and low cost. While various types of feeds can be used with patch antennas to connect the antenna element to input/output connections, a probe type feed is a popular choice with the connection on the back side of the antenna. Patch antennas are typically mounted over a ground plane and have limited control on the radiation characteristics. [1] Areas of high directivity are typically directed in the upper hemi-sphere (i.e., towards the satellites for GNSS applications) and areas of low-directivity are typically directed downward (i.e., below the ground plane). Variations of single-element patch antennas have been implemented to limit the multipath using complex ground plane structures [1], such as choke rings [2] [3], complex ground planes structures [4] [5], or circuitry [6].

In an interference/jamming/spoofing environment, single-element patch antennas have limited ability to suppress these interference sources to enhance performance. Antenna arrays are very common when the performance requirements exceed the capabilities of a single-element antenna. Antenna arrays use multiple antenna elements that are geometrically distributed to aid in obtaining the performance requirements. Antenna arrays are physically larger than single-element antennas that are within a given antenna array. Elements within an antenna array may be provided with amplitude and phase control to change the antenna pattern of the array, but the antenna array is physically larger than an individual antenna element within the array. Multi-element controlled reception pattern antenna (CRPA) has been used in the GNSS community to enhance the performance in an interference/jamming/spoofing environment. [7] [8].

II. SINGLE-APETURE ANTENNA DESIGN

A. Overview of Design Approach

This paper presents an innovative single-aperture (i.e., single-element) patch antenna with the ability to have pattern control by placing multiple feeds on opposite ends of the antenna element, and controlling the amplitude and phase distribution of each of the feed ports. The amplitude and phase control subsystem may be performed by an amplitude and phase control circuit or performed in software. The feeds are then joined by a combiner subsystem. This work will concentrate on a 4-feed network design connected to a single patch aperture where the phase control and feed combination is done in hardware. Fig. 1 illustrates a block diagram of how this single-aperture antenna is configured with separate RF front-end circuitry, amplitude & phase control, a combiner, and GNSS receiver functionality. The GNSS receiver functionality can be accomplished with a traditional type single-RF input receiver or a digital, software defined radio (SDR) type GNSS receiver. In a GNSS SDR receiver configuration, certain functions such as RF front-end, amplitude & phase control, and combining functions may be done within the SDR.

Fig. 1. Single-aperture Antenna with Pattern Control with GNSS Receiver Functions

Under benign conditions, the four ports can be combined for right hand circular polarization (RHCP) operation with uniform radiation intensity in the upper hemisphere. When interference/jamming/spoofing is detected and localized, then this single-aperture antenna can direct an area of low-radiation intensity in that direction.

Pattern control in the azimuth direction is obtained by varying the phase of adjacent ports as well as having control on the elevation pattern by varying the phase of opposite ports. This phase control is performed on a quadrant-by-quadrant basis. The pattern may be controlled in such a way to direct high levels of radiation intensity in a particular direction. The pattern may also be controlled in such a way to direct low levels of radiation intensity in a particular direction.

To demonstrate the pattern control of this single-aperture patch antenna design, a single-frequency GNSS antenna was designed and implemented. The antenna was designed to primarily support the GPS L5 and Galileo E5a band centered at 1176.45 MHz. [9] [10] The design was based on a circular patch and circular ground plane. A Rogers TMM10i substrate material was selected for implementation. The geometry of this patch antenna design concentrated on circular geometry for the patch element, substrate, feed ports, and ground plane to avoid any asymmetry that may be introduced by an asymmetric antenna configuration. [11]

The initial design dimensions of the patch antenna were estimated with an analytical cavity model using (1). [12].

$$a = \frac{F}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2h}{\pi \epsilon_r F \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{\pi F}{2h} \right) + 1.7726 \right\}}}} \quad (1)$$

where :

$$F = \frac{8.791 \times 10^9}{f_r \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$$

a = radius of the patch, [cm]

h = thickness of the patch substrate, [cm]

ϵ_r = relative permittivity of substrate, [unitless]

f_r = desired resonance frequency, [Hz]

This innovative pattern control for a single-element (i.e., single-aperture) patch antenna was first presented at ION GNSS+ 2015, [13], where high-fidelity computational electromagnetic models (CEM) were used to introduce this technique. The CEM results will be summarized in the next section to illustrate the design.

Following the CEM design, this paper presented measured results of this design which further demonstrates the pattern control of this single-aperture patch antenna. Data at the component level (i.e., port level) and radiation characteristics using the Ohio University Shielded Antenna Anechoic Chamber will be presented.

B. Computational Electromagnetic Model of Design

The antenna was initially designed from the analytical cavity model using (1) and refined with the aid of a high-fidelity CEM, Computer Simulation Technology (CST) software. [14] The CEM CST was used and various phase combinations were performed in a post-process fashion to illustrate the beam control in azimuth and elevation. [13]. The Rogers TMM 10i substrate material, of height 5.08 mm provided good resonance at the GPS L5 and Galileo E5a center frequency of 1176.45 MHz, with a diameter of 50.25 mm. Each of the four feeds were placed 10.75 mm from the center of the patch, which provided a good nominal impedance match to 50 Ω . The circular patch element is small enough to be confined to the common ARINC 743A footprint. [15] To help minimize simulation time, a 200 mm circular ground plane was used in the simulations.

Table 1 illustrates the overall phase control approach where the phase on each of the ports is shifted over on a quadrant-by-quadrant basis. For each quadrant, a respective port is chosen for reference phase (i.e., 0 deg), and the next port phase is selected with the nominal polarization in mind. The phase opposite to the reference port (e.g., port 4 for Quadrant 1), i.e., $\Delta\gamma_{ADJ}$ is adjusted to move the area of high directivity (and commensurate area of low directivity) in azimuth. Elevation control of the area of high directivity (and commensurate area of low directivity) is controlled using the $\Delta\gamma_{OPP}$ phase control parameter, again on a quadrant-by-quadrant basis.

TABLE I. ILLUSTRATED PHASE CONTROL SETTINGS FOR GNSS CIRCULAR PATCH ANTENNA WITH PATTERN CONTROL

Quadrant	Port Number			
	1	2	3	4
1	0	90	$\Delta\gamma_{OPP}$	$\Delta\gamma_{ADJ}$
2	90	$\Delta\gamma_{OPP}$	$\Delta\gamma_{ADJ}$	0
3	$\Delta\gamma_{OPP}$	$\Delta\gamma_{ADJ}$	0	90
4	$\Delta\gamma_{ADJ}$	0	90	$\Delta\gamma_{OPP}$

Ideally, the radiation characteristics of the circular patch antenna over a circular ground plane will be symmetric in all directions, as illustrated in Fig.2. [13], where this baseline performance is identified as Step 0, with desired phase of [0 90 180 270] on ports [1 2 3 4], respectively. This will provide for nominal RHCP reception. The CEM output plots are viewed “from the top” looking straight down onto the top of the antenna. Various aspects of the radiation characteristics will be described with respect to the phi angle, which is measured in the xy plane, from the +x axis towards the +y axis.

Fig. 2. Step 0: Single-aperture Patch Antenna over Circular Ground Plane Pattern Controlled with phases: [0 90 180 270]. (Top View), [13]

To provide a sample of the pattern control from the CEM simulations, consider the azimuth pattern control where the port phases [1 2 3 4] are set to produce the area of high gain (and commensurate area of low gain), towards each of the four axis directions (i.e., phi= 270, 0, 90, and 180 deg in that order). While in the previous CEM simulations, steps in azimuth were taken every 10 deg [13], here the steps will be 90 deg, so the Steps identified in [13] will be used for comparison purposes. Fig. 3 illustrates Step 5, with the desired phases of [0 90 20 90], where the area of high directivity is obtained towards the phi=180deg direction, and an area of low directivity is obtained towards phi=90deg.

Fig. 3. Step 5: Single-aperture Patch Antenna over Circular Ground Plane Pattern Controlled with phases: [0 90 20 90]. (Top View), [13]

Figure 4 illustrates Step 14, with the desired phases of [90 20 90 0], where the area of high directivity is obtained towards the phi=0deg direction and an area of low directivity is obtained towards the phi=180deg direction.

Fig. 4. Step 14: Single-aperture Patch Antenna over Circular Ground Plane Pattern Controlled with phases: [90 20 90 0]. (Top View), [13]

Figure 5 illustrates Step 23, with the desired phases of [20 90 0 90], where the area of high directivity is obtained in the phi=90deg direction and an area of low directivity is obtained towards the phi=270deg direction.

Fig. 5. Step 23: Single-aperture Patch Antenna over Circular Ground Plane Pattern Controlled with phases: [20, 90, 0, 90]. (Top View), [13]

Figure 6 illustrates Step 32, with the desired phases of [90 0 90 20], where the area of high directivity is obtained to the $\phi=180$ deg direction and an area of low directivity is obtained towards in the $\phi=0$ deg direction.

Fig. 6. Step 32: Single-aperture Patch Antenna over Circular Ground Plane Pattern Controlled with phases: [90, 0, 90, 20]. (Top View), [13]

III. FABRICATION AND TEST

A. Fabrication

The output DXF file information from the CEM simulation was applied to a computer numerical controlled (CNC) milling machine located in the Ohio University, Russ College of Engineering and Technology machine shop. SubMiniature version B (SMB) connectors were placed at each of the feed locations and the center pin of each connector was soldered to the top of the patch element. At the center of the patch antenna, a grounding pin was implemented via a 2mm stainless steel machine screw with a nut on the bottom of the ground plane, which helped secure the antenna to the ground plane.

Figure 7 is a photograph of the single-aperture GNSS patch antenna for the GPS L5 frequency. The antenna was designed

to resonate at the center frequency of the GPS L5 1176.45 MHz with no radome to demonstrate the pattern control. While the CEM simulations were performed with a 120 mm ground plane (copper ground plane in Fig. 7), the antenna and copper ground plane was mounted on a 2 foot diameter ground plane for anechoic chamber testing (gray ground plane in Fig. 7). The port numbers and orientation of the antenna is the same as the previous CEM simulations. [13]

Fig. 7. Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna (GNSS L5 configuration without radome)

B. Component Level Testing

After the antenna was fabricated, it was tested at the component level using an Agilent 8753ES Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). All testing used [16] and [17] for guidance. The antenna was mounted on a 2 foot diameter aluminum ground plane and S11 return loss and standing wave ratio (SWR) measurements were recorded. These measurements did include an SMB-to-SMA cable adaptor, which was approximately 6" in length. Fig. 8 illustrates the SWR measurements for each port. Each port provided an excellent match to a nominal 50 Ω impedance, and excellent repeatability from port to port. These data indicate that each port can support a bandwidth on the order of 100 MHz, using a 2:1 SWR as a metric. It should be noted that this is a very good bandwidth for a patch antenna, which is a characteristic for the circular geometry. [18] With additional tuning by making the diameter of the patch antenna slightly smaller, the antenna would be able to additionally support the Galileo E5b[10] and the GPS L2 (centered at 1227.60 MHz) bands [19].

Fig. 8. Measured Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna (GNSS L5 configuration), standing wave ratio (SWR) at each port.

C. Anechoic Chamber Testing

With the excellent data from each of the ports characterized, the antenna radiation patterns were characterized using the Ohio University Shielded Antenna Anechoic Chamber. [20] The chamber measures 13 ft by 13 ft by 26 ft to provide for direct far-field measurements using an L-band RHCP helix transmission antenna as the source. The helix antenna had 5 turns and was built in-house. The single-aperture patch antenna on a 2 ft ground plane was mounted vertically within the anechoic chambers, which was rotated to obtain “elevation” cuts, every 1 deg and 36 cuts at various “azimuth” angles (i.e., elevation cuts every 5deg in phi) to characterize the radiation intensity of the antenna. Tests performed with 36 elevation cuts (every phi=5 deg) allowed for a more qualitative visual 3D representation of the antenna pattern characterization, with two orthogonal cuts, plotted in 2D provided more quantitative data for analysis.

The anechoic chamber measurement systems utilized the same Agilent 8753ES VNA used for the component level testing, that transmitted sufficient transmission power for phase control, so no RF amplification was added directly after each of the antenna ports. For the demonstration of the pattern control, equal amplitude weights were applied to each port and phase control for each port was implemented with USB controlled Vaunix Lab Brick LPS-202 Phase Shifters, followed by a Mini-Circuits ZA4PD-2 4:1 signal combiner. Both the phase shifters and signal combiner were mounted on the backside of the 2 ft ground plane and covered with anechoic material to help minimize signal reflections. The phase shifter controlling computer was placed outside the shielded anechoic chamber and connected to the USB controlled phase shifters via a 4:1 powered USB hub and a powered 21 ft USB cable. Once the received L5 RF signal came back into the control room, it was amplified to provide a good phase measurement by the VNA. The common path amplification circuit consisted of a ferrite isolator and two dual-stage L-band amplifiers fed with bias-Ts. Fig. 9 is a photograph of the anechoic chamber set-up where the antenna under test (AUT) is shown on a dielectric tower,

which rotates to provide “elevation” and “azimuth” plane performance radiation characterization of the antenna.

Fig. 9. Anechoic Chamber Testing of the Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna (Back side of antenna ground plane shown in foreground)

System calibration was performed in various steps prior to pattern characterization data collection. First, the performance of each of the phase shifters was investigated on the bench directly connected to the VNA and each provided good gain and phase stability within their specification limits. Next, with the antenna and power combiner in place (temporarily bypassing each of the phase shifters), the performance of the RHCP helix antenna at boresight was investigated. For the first AUT port (with the other three AUT ports loaded), the RHCP helix antenna was rotated in 90deg steps. While the measured phase difference paths at each RHCP helix positions should vary by exactly 90deg, it was noticed that it was slightly off, which would indicate a slight phase imbalance in the RHCP helix transmission antenna.

To further investigate the RHCP helix transmission phase imbalance, the RHCP helix antenna was fixed, and the AUT was rotated in 90deg steps, measuring the through phase for each AUT port, at each of the AUT port locations. Here, each of the four AUT ports was connected, one at a time (with the other three output antenna ports loaded), and each of the complete phase paths was measured individually, at each of the four port locations (i.e., in 90deg steps in phi). While the phase measurement for each of the reception paths, at each port location should have been exactly 90deg different, it was noticed that the average phase varied by as much as 12 deg from the nominal 90deg, where the average measured phase differences, across the four ports and four port locations was: 94.8, 78.2, 103.4, and 79.2 deg (differences from the nominal by 4.8, 11.8, 13.4, and 10.8 deg). This helped confirm the phase imbalance believed to be from the L-band RHCP helix transmission antenna at the L5 center frequency on boresight.

Next, calibration was performed with each phase shifter connected in each path, individually, with the other three antenna output ports loaded; this calibration was performed at boresight for both the RHCP helix antenna and AUT, with both

the RHCP helix transmission antenna and AUT fixed. For each one of these paths, the power was measured and the phase was measured when the respective phase shifter was commanded in 10 deg increments. The complete path measured phase, for each of the paths was recorded and a phase calibration table was built. This phase calibration table was then used to command the desired phases on each port.

1) Step 0: Baseline, with phases [0 90 180 270]

Baseline testing, Step 0, was first performed so that it could be used for comparison and analysis for the pattern control of the single-aperture antenna. For the baseline configuration, the phases to each of the ports [1 2 3 4] were desired to have phases of [0 90 180 270] deg, respectively. Using the phase calibration table, the phases commanded to the phase shifters were {311 26 109 213} deg, respectively. Data were collected over 36 elevation cuts (i.e., every 5deg in phi), including various orthogonal cuts to produce both 3D qualitative and 2D quantitative assessments of the radiation characteristics. Fig. 10 shows the measured 3D qualitative depiction of the baseline radiation characteristics for the desired phase settings for Step 0: [0 90 180 270], which shows excellent symmetric coverage in the upper hemi-sphere.

Fig. 10. Step 0: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna (Baseline) with desired phase of [0 90 180 270], measured 3D radiation characteristics.

Figure 11 illustrates the measured radiation characteristics of the antenna in the two principle planes for the baseline configuration. Each of the ports identified in Fig. 7 are labeled as “P” in Fig. 11, as will be done in the remainder of this paper. Also, for each of the 2D radiation characteristics plots, the left side (LS), and right side (RS) of each trace is identified in the particular azimuth (i.e., phi) direction for the plot. Thus, in Fig. 11, the first cut executed in the chamber testing is the red (dash-dot-dash) trace which measures the radiation characteristics in the P1 & P3 plane (i.e., xz plane), from P1 to P3, so, phi=0deg is on the LS of the figure and phi=180deg is on the RS of the figure. Then the AUT rotates 90deg in the xy plane, and then stops, to measure the radiation characteristics in the perpendicular P2 & P4 plane (i.e., yz plane) from P4 to P2, so phi=270deg is on the RS and phi=90deg is on the LS.

Fig. 11. Step 0: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna (Baseline) with desired phase of [0 90 180 270], measured 2D radiation characteristics, along principle axes.

As can be seen in Figures 10 and 11, the baseline performance had excellent symmetry in the radiation characteristics and is consistent with the CEM simulations, as shown in Fig. 2.

2) Step 5: “First Quadrant” Pattern Control with phase [0 90 80 90]

To provide an illustration of the pattern control capability of the single-aperture patch antenna, the phases of the ports were commanded to provide a null (i.e., area of low directivity, with a commensurate area of high directivity) in each of four axis directions. For all of these tests, the elevation phase control value was set to 80deg. For Step 5, the desired phases are then [0 90 80 90], which would produce the area of high directivity towards the phi=270deg direction and the area of low gain in the phi=90deg direction (CEM simulations of Fig. 3). Data were collected over 36 elevation cuts, including various orthogonal cuts to produce both 3D qualitative and 2D quantitative assessments of the radiation characteristics.

To illustrate this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control, Fig. 12 shows the measured 3D qualitative depiction of the radiation characteristics for the desired phase settings for Step 5: [0 90 80 90]. (Using the phase calibration table, the actual commanded phases to the phase shifters were {311 26 11 34}.) The data contained in Fig. 12 shows the area of low gain in the phi=90 deg direction, and provides good coverage otherwise, with the area of high directivity towards the phi=270deg direction. These results are consistent with the results from the CEM simulations; see Fig 3.

Fig. 12. Step 5: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [0 90 80 90], measured 3D radiation characteristics.

It should be noted that the null commanded to the $\phi=90$ deg direction is slightly off from the $+y$ axis. While the null direction could be commanded to more precisely align the null (i.e., area of low directivity) in the $+y$ direction by adjusting the $\Delta\gamma_{adj}$ parameter on port 4 for this first quadrant [13], this pointing error characterization is useful to help further improve the effectiveness of this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control technique. It is believed that this slight pointing error of the null (i.e., area of low directivity) is due to the helix antenna phase offsets and/or the phase calibration that was done only at boresight.

To illustrate in more detail, the measured 2D radiation characteristics are shown in Fig. 13 for the same phase settings as in Fig. 12 along the principle axes. The area of low gain is more precisely illustrated in the $\phi=90$ deg direction (green dashed trace on LS). It should be noted that this is precisely in the yz plane and this elevation cut is not directly in the null direction. Hence, there is additional gain suppression beyond what is illustrated in Fig. 13. From the data in Fig. 13, with reference to the baseline performance shown in Fig. 11, it can be seen that the gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is on the order of 12-13 dB at the horizon, and suppression is provided at, above, and below the horizon. This directivity reduction is believed to be useful for interference suppression for a given set of commanded phases on the ports.

Fig. 13. Step 5: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [0 90 80 90], measured 2D radiation characteristics, along principle axes.

To investigate the gain suppression performance towards the null direction in the designated “first quadrant”, the data was processed, with 5deg resolution in azimuth. Fig. 14 illustrates the null performance in the $\phi=75$ deg direction (green dashed trace on the LS), along with the perpendicular performance (red dash-dot-dash trace). As can be seen on the LS of Fig. 14, in the null direction, there is significant gain suppression at, above, and below the horizon, with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., red dash-dot-dash trace) as illustrated in Fig. 14, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11. Furthermore, the null depth is shown to be on the order of 22-28 dB with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., red dash-dot-dash trace) as illustrated in Fig. 14, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11.

Fig. 14. Step 5: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [0 90 80 90], measured 2D radiation characteristics, illustrating null performance.

3) Step 14: “Second Quadrant” Pattern Control with phase [90 80 90 0]

Next, to further illustrate the pattern control of this single-aperture patch antenna, the phases of the ports were commanded to the next quadrant, identified as Step 14, which would put the area of high directivity in the $\phi=0^\circ$ direction and the area of low directivity in the $\phi=180^\circ$ direction; see Fig. 4 for the CEM simulation results.

To illustrate this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control, Fig. 15 shows two measured 3D qualitative depictions of the radiation characteristics for the desired phase settings for Step 14: [90 80 90 0]. (Using the phase calibration table, the actual commanded phases to the phase shifters were {45 16 19 302}.) Here, two 3D plots are shown due to the x axis in the opposite direction of the area of low directivity. The data contained in Fig. 15 show the area of low gain towards the $\phi=180^\circ$ deg direction, and provides good coverage otherwise, with the area of high directivity towards the $\phi=0^\circ$ deg direction. These results are consistent with the results from the CEM simulations; see Fig 4.

Fig. 15. Step 14: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 80 90 0], measured 3D radiation characteristics.

It should be noted that the null commanded to the $\phi=180^\circ$ deg direction is slightly off from the $-x$ axis. While the null direction could be commanded to more precisely align the null (i.e., area of low directivity) in the $-x$ direction by adjusting the $\Delta\gamma_{adj}$ parameter on port 3 for this second quadrant [13], this pointing error characterization is useful to help further improve the effectiveness of this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control technique. It is believed that this slight pointing error of the null (i.e., area of low directivity) is due to the helix antenna phase offsets and/or the phase calibration that was done only at boresight.

To illustrate in more detail, the measured 2D radiation characteristics are shown in Fig. 16 for the same phase settings as in Fig. 15 along the principle axes. The area of low directivity is more precisely illustrated towards the $\phi=180^\circ$ deg direction (red dash-dot-dash trace, on RS). It should be noted that this is precisely in the xz plane and this elevation cut is not directly in the null direction. Hence, there is additional gain suppression beyond what is illustrated in Fig. 16. From the data in Fig. 16, with reference to the baseline performance shown in Fig. 11, it can be seen that the gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is on the order of 4-5 dB at the horizon, and suppression is provided at, above, and below the horizon. This directivity reduction is believed to be useful for interference suppression for a given set of commanded phases on the ports.

Fig. 16. Step 14: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 80 90 0], measured 2D radiation characteristics, along principle axes.

To investigate the gain suppression performance towards the null direction in the designated “second quadrant”, the data was processed, with 5deg resolution in azimuth. Fig. 17 illustrates the null performance in the $\phi=170$ deg direction (red dash-dot-dash trace on the RS), along with the perpendicular performance (green dashed trace). As can be seen on the RS of Fig. 17, in the null direction, there is significant gain suppression at the horizon, above, and below the horizon, with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., green dashed trace) as illustrated in Fig 17, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11. Furthermore, the null depth is shown to be on the order of 35 dB with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., red dash-dot-dash trace) as illustrated in Fig 14, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11.

Fig. 17. Step 14: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 80 90 0], measured 2D radiation characteristics, illustrating null performance.

4) Step 23: “Third Quadrant” Pattern Control with phase [80 90 0 90]

Next, to further illustrate the pattern control of this single-aperture patch antenna, the phases of the ports were commanded to the next quadrant, identified as Step 23, which would put the area of high directivity in the $\phi=90$ deg direction and the area of low directivity in the $\phi=270$ deg direction; see Fig. 5 for the CEM simulation results.

To illustrate this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control, Fig. 18 shows two measured 3D qualitative depictions of the radiation characteristics for the desired phase settings for Step 23: [80 90 0 90]. (Using the phase calibration table, the actual commanded phases to the phase shifters were {35 26 290 34}.) Here, two 3D plots are shown due to the y axis in the opposite direction of the area of low directivity. The data contained in Fig. 18 show the area of low gain in the $\phi=270$ deg direction, and provides good coverage otherwise, with the area of high directivity towards the $\phi=90$ deg direction. These results are consistent with the results from the CEM simulations; see Fig 5.

Fig. 18. Step 23: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [80 90 0 90], measured 3D radiation characteristics.

It should be noted that the null commanded to the $\phi=270$ deg direction is slightly off from the $-y$ axis. While the null direction could be commanded to more precisely align the null (i.e., area of low directivity) in the $-y$ direction by adjusting the $\Delta\gamma_{adj}$ parameter on port 2 for this third quadrant [13], this pointing error characterization is useful to help further improve the effectiveness of this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control technique. It is believed that this slight pointing error of the null (i.e., area of low directivity) is due to the helix antenna phase offsets and/or the phase calibration that was done only at boresight.

To illustrate in more detail, the measured 2D radiation characteristics are shown in Fig. 19 for the same phase settings as in Fig. 18 along the principle axes. The area of low gain is more precisely illustrated in the $\phi=270$ deg direction (green dashed trace, on RS). It should be noted that this is precisely in the yz plane and this elevation cut is not directly in the null direction. Hence, there is additional gain suppression beyond what is illustrated in Fig. 19. From the data in Fig. 19, with reference to the baseline performance shown in Fig. 11, it can be seen that the gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is on the order of 5-7 dB at the horizon, and suppression is provided more significantly at positive elevation angles. This directivity reduction is believed to be useful for interference suppression for a given set of commanded phases on the ports.

Fig. 19. Step 23: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [80 90 0 90], measured 2D radiation characteristics, along principle axes.

To investigate the gain suppression performance towards the null direction in the designated “third quadrant”, the data was processed, with 5deg resolution in azimuth. Fig. 20 illustrates the null performance in the $\phi=75$ deg direction (green dashed trace on the RS), along with the perpendicular performance (red dash-dot-dash trace). As can be seen on the RS of Fig. 20, in the null direction, there is significant gain suppression at, above, and below the horizon, with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., red dash-dot-dash trace) as illustrated in Fig 20, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11. Furthermore, the null depth is shown to be on the order of 35 dB with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., red dash-dot-dash trace) as illustrated in Fig 20, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11.

--- P1 & P3 plane, LS: $\phi = 345$ deg, RS: $\phi = 165$ deg
 --- P2 & P4 plane, LS: $\phi = 75$ deg, RS: $\phi = 255$ deg

Fig. 20. Step 23: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [80 90 0 90], measured 2D radiation characteristics, illustrating null performance.

5) Step 32: “Forth Quadrant” Pattern Control with phase [90 0 90 80]

Lastly, to illustrate the pattern control of this single-aperture patch antenna, the phases of the ports were commanded to the next quadrant, identified as Step 32, which would put the area of high directivity in the $\phi=180$ deg direction and the area of low directivity in the $\phi=0$ deg direction; see Fig. 6 for the CEM simulation results.

To illustrate this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control, Fig. 21 shows the measured 3D qualitative depiction of the radiation characteristics for the desired phase settings for Step 32: [90 0 90 80]. (Using the phase calibration table, the actual commanded phases to the phase shifters were {45 295 19 24}.) The data contained in Fig. 21 shows the area of low directivity towards the $\phi=0$ deg direction, and provides good coverage otherwise, with the area of high directivity towards the $\phi=180$ deg direction. These results are consistent with the results from the CEM simulations; see Fig 6.

Fig. 21. Step 14: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 0 90 80], measured 3D radiation characteristics.

Again, it should be noted that the null commanded to the $\phi=0$ deg direction is slightly off from the $+x$ axis. While the null direction could be commanded to more precisely align the null (i.e., area of low directivity) in the $+x$ direction by adjusting the $\Delta\gamma_{adj}$ parameter on port 1 for this fourth quadrant [13], this pointing error characterization is useful to help further improve the effectiveness of this single-aperture patch antenna with pattern control technique. It is believed that this slight pointing error of the null (i.e., area of low directivity) is due to the helix antenna phase offsets and/or the phase calibration that was done only at boresight.

To illustrate in more detail, the measured 2D radiation characteristics are shown in Fig. 22 for the same phase settings as in Fig. 21 along the principle axes. The area of low directivity is more precisely illustrated towards the $\phi=0$ deg direction (red dash-dot-dash trace, on LS). It should be noted that this is precisely in the xz plane and this elevation cut is not directly in the null direction. Hence, there is additional gain suppression beyond what is illustrated in Fig. 22. From the data in Fig. 22, with reference to the baseline performance shown in Fig. 11, it can be seen that the gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is on the order of 12-13 dB at the horizon, and suppression is provided at, above, and below the horizon. This directivity reduction is believed to be useful for interference suppression for a given set of commanded phases on the ports.

Fig. 22. Step 32: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 0 90 80], measured 2D radiation characteristics, along principle axes.

To investigate the gain suppression performance towards the null direction in the designated “fourth quadrant”, the data was processed, with 5deg resolution in azimuth. Fig. 23 illustrates the null performance in the $\phi=345$ deg direction (red dash-dot-dash trace on the LS), along with the perpendicular performance (green dashed trace). As can be seen on the LS of Fig. 23, in the null direction, there is significant gain suppression at, above, and below the horizon, with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., green dashed trace) as illustrated in Fig. 23, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11. Furthermore, the null depth is shown to be on the order of 30 dB with reference to either the perpendicular cut (i.e., green dashed trace) as illustrated in Fig. 23, or with reference to the nominal performance illustrated in Fig. 11.

Fig. 23. Step 32: Single-aperture GNSS Patch Antenna with desired phases of [90 0 90 80], measured 2D radiation characteristics, illustrating null performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a single-aperture (i.e., single-element) GNSS patch antenna that can electronically control the radiation characteristic, by placing an area of high directivity with a commensurate area of low directivity in a particular direction that may be useful for interference suppression. Here, the performance of a circular four probe-fed GPS L5 patch antenna over a circular ground plane is illustrated with an amplitude and phase control subsystem for pattern control. The overall design approach is outlined and supported with computational electromagnetic model (CEM) simulations and measured results. The fabrication of the antenna is illustrated and measured results at the component level and antenna anechoic chamber radiation characteristics illustrate the pattern control aspects of the antenna and provides for gain (i.e., directivity) suppression at, above, and below the horizon at a commanded azimuth angle. This control has a major advantage by controlling the radiation characteristics to enable mitigation of interfering signals.

This paper contains simulated and measured performance data of an innovative single-aperture patch antenna with the ability to have pattern control by placing multiple feeds on opposite ends of the antenna element and controlling the amplitude and phase distribution of each of the feed ports. The advantage of this approach is that a nominal RHCP antenna pattern can be achieved under benign conditions, and pattern control can be achieved under interference/jamming/spoofing conditions. Measured component (i.e., port) data provides good impedance match at the GPS L5 frequency and bandwidth on

each port on the order of 100 MHz, which is very good for a patch antenna.

Measured antenna anechoic chamber results illustrate the pattern control for this single-aperture patch antenna to provide a null at various commanded azimuth (i.e., ϕ) angles to enable interference suppression. Gain (i.e., directivity) suppression is achieved at, above, and below the horizon in the commanded null direction, with gain suppression at the horizon varying from 4-13 dB. Null depth were achieved that vary from 22-35 dB. The author believes the performance of the commanded pattern control can be further enhanced with increased calibration. These results clearly indicate that pattern control is achieved for this single-aperture patch antenna utilizing this four-feed control network and quadrant-by-quadrant phase control technique. The author believes that this is the first time such pattern control has been achieved and demonstrated with measured data for a small single-aperture patch antenna.

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